

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

List of appendices for:

Thesis for national diploma of doctor of dental medicine

**The future of precision orthodontics: integration of technology and
biomedicine into customized therapy**

BY

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Monastir, on the 02nd of February 2022

Thesis candidate

Jihed M'hamed

Appendix 1-A: Search strategy in electronic databases.

1/ Artificial Intelligence: (897 results)

PUBMED: 476 results

("Orthodontics"[Mesh] OR orthodontic*) AND ("Artificial Intelligence"[Mesh] OR (artificial intelligen*) OR (deep learning) OR (machine learning) OR (neural networks) OR (computer aided orthodontic diagnosis) OR (automated orthodontic diagnosis))

EBSCO host: 60 results

TX (orthodontic*) AND AB (((artificial intelligen*) OR (deep learning) OR (machine learning) OR (neural networks) OR (computer aided orthodontic diagnosis) OR (automated orthodontic diagnosis)))

SCIENCE Direct: 95 results

Find articles with these terms: (orthodontic OR orthodontics)
Title, abstract or author-specified keywords: ((artificial intelligence) OR (deep learning) OR (machine learning) OR (neural networks) OR (computer aided orthodontic diagnosis) OR (automated orthodontic diagnosis))
Excluded: short communications, book chapters, conference abstracts

SCOPUS: 115 results

((TITLE-ABS-KEY ((orthodontic*)) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (((artificial AND intelligen*) OR (deep AND learning) OR (machine AND learning) OR (neural AND networks) OR (computer AND aided AND orthodontic AND diagnosis) OR (automated AND orthodontic AND diagnosis))))) AND PUBYEAR > 1999 AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "re")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English") OR LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "French"))
Limitations: French & English / Articles & Reviews

Web of Science: 151 results

TS=(orthodontic*) AND TS=((artificial intelligen*) OR (deep learning) OR (machine learning) OR (neural networks) OR (computer aided orthodontic diagnosis) OR (automated orthodontic diagnosis))
 Refined by: DOCUMENT TYPES: (ARTICLE OR REVIEW OR EARLY ACCESS OR CLINICAL TRIAL) AND LANGUAGES: (ENGLISH OR FRENCH)
 Timespan: 2000-2021. Databases: WOS, KJD, MEDLINE, RSCI, SCIELO.

2/ Nanotechnology: (703 results)

PUBMED: 392 results

("Orthodontics"[Mesh] OR orthodontic*[tiab]) AND ("Nanotechnology"[Mesh] OR "Nanoparticles"[Mesh] OR nanotechnolog*[tw] OR nanomedicine[tw] OR nano*[tiab])

EBSCO host: 80 results

((AB (orthodontic*)) OR (TI (orthodontic*))) AND TI (((nanotechnolog*) OR (nanomedicine) OR (nano*)))

SCIENCE Direct: 25 results

Title, abstract or author-specified keywords: (orthodontic OR orthodontics) AND ((nanotechnology) OR (nanomedicine) OR (nano))

Filters: included only review and research articles

SCOPUS: 94 results

((TITLE ((orthodontic*)) AND TITLE (((nanotechnolog*) OR (nanomedicine) OR (nano*))))) AND PUBYEAR > 1999 AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "re")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English") OR LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "French"))

Web of Science: 112 results

(TI=(orthodontic*)) AND (TI=((nanotechnolog*) OR (nanomedicine) OR (nano*)))

Refined by: DOCUMENT TYPES: (ARTICLE OR CLINICAL TRIAL OR REVIEW) AND LANGUAGES: (ENGLISH)

Timespan: 2000-2021. Databases: WOS, KJD, MEDLINE, RSCI, SCIELO.

3/ Regenerative Therapy: STEM CELLS & PRF: (318 results)

PUBMED: 194 results

("Orthodontics"[Mesh] OR orthodontic*[tiab]) AND ("Stem Cells"[Mesh] OR (stem cell*[tiab]) OR "Platelet-Rich Fibrin"[Mesh] OR (Platelet-Rich Fibrin[tiab]) OR (PRF[tw]))

EBSCO host: 52 results

((AB (orthodontic*)) OR (TI (orthodontic*))) AND TI (((stem cell*) OR (Platelet-Rich Fibrin) OR (PRF)))

SCIENCE Direct: 32 results

Title, abstract or author-specified keywords: (orthodontic OR orthodontics) AND ((stem cell) OR (Platelet-Rich Fibrin) OR (PRF))

Filters: excluded book chapters, short communications, conference abstracts

SCOPUS: 20 results

((TITLE ((orthodontic*)) AND TITLE (((stem AND cell*) OR (platelet-rich AND fibrin) OR (prf)))) AND PUBYEAR > 1999 AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "re")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English") OR LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "French"))

Web of Science: 20 results

(TI=(orthodontic*)) AND (TI=((stem cell) OR (Platelet-Rich Fibrin) OR (PRF)))

Refined by: DOCUMENT TYPES: (ARTICLE OR REVIEW) AND LANGUAGES: (ENGLISH)

Timespan: 2000-2021. Databases: WOS, KJD, MEDLINE, RSCI, SCIELO.

Appendix 1-B: Search strategy results in electronic databases.

Artificial intelligence:

- ❖ PubMed (from 1st January 2000 until 9th January 2021): The search resulted in 476 published works.

The screenshot shows the PubMed.gov search interface. The search query is: ("Orthodontics"[Mesh] OR orthodontic*) AND ("Artificial Intelligence"[Mesh] OR artificial intelligence*). The results page shows 476 results, with a red box highlighting this number. The first result is: [Recent progress of robots in stomatology]. Liu DD, Zhao WD, Niu J, Li D, Zhou ZY, Zhang JY, Liu XQ. Hua Xi Kou Qiang Yi Xue Za Zhi. 2020 Feb 1;38(1):90-94. doi: 10.7518/hxkq.2020.01.016. PMID: 32037773. Free PMC article. Chinese. The second result is: Bone age assessment based on deep convolution neural network incorporated with segmentation. Gao Y, Zhu T, Xu X. Int J Comput Assist Radiol Surg. 2020 Dec 15(12):1951-1962. doi: 10.1007/s11548-020-02266-0. Epub ahead of print. The interface includes filters for text availability (Abstract, Free full text) and a results by year chart.

Figure 1: PubMed AI search results

- ❖ EBSCO host (from 1st January 2000 until 9th January 2021): The search resulted in 60 published works.

The screenshot shows the EBSCO host search interface. The search query is: TX (orthodontic*) AND AB ((artificial intelligen*). The results page shows 60 results, with a red box highlighting "Search Results: 1 - 10 of 60". The first result is: 1. Deep learning-based dental plaque detection on primary teeth: a comparison with clinical assessments. By: You, Wenzhe; Hao, Aimin; Li, Shuai; Wang, Yong; Xia, Bin. BMC Oral Health. 5/13/2020, Vol. 20 Issue 1, p1-7. 7p. DOI: 10.1186/s12903-020-01114-6. Background: Dental plaque causes many common oral diseases (e.g., caries, gingivitis, and periodontitis). Therefore, plaque detection and control are extremely important for children's oral health... Subjects: ARTIFICIAL intelligence; DENTAL plaque; DENTISTS; ORAL hygiene; PEDIATRIC dentistry; T-test (Statistics); DECIDUOUS dentition (Tooth development); DEEP learning; CHILDREN. The interface includes a refine results sidebar with filters for Boolean/Phrase, Expanders, Language, and a search history section.

Figure 2: EBSCO host AI search results

- ❖ ScienceDirect (from 1st January 2000 until 9th January 2021): The search resulted in 95 published works.

The screenshot shows the ScienceDirect search interface. At the top, the search terms are '(orthodontic OR orthodontics)' and the year range is '2000-2021'. The search results are sorted by relevance. A red box highlights '95 results'. The first result is a review article titled 'Smartphone applications used in orthodontics: A scoping review of scholarly literature' by Nikhilesh R. Vaid, Ismaeel Hansa, and Yashodhan Bichu, published in the Journal of the World Federation of Orthodontists in September 2020. The second result is a systematic review titled 'Scope and performance of artificial intelligence technology in orthodontic diagnosis, treatment planning, and clinical decision-making - A systematic review' by Sanjeev B. Khanagar, Ali Al-Ehaideb, and Sachin S. Sarode, published in the Journal of Dental Sciences in June 2020.

Figure 3: ScienceDirect AI search results

- ❖ Scopus (from 1st January 2000 until 9th January 2021): The search resulted in 115 published works.

The screenshot shows the Scopus search interface. The search results are displayed as a table with columns for Document title, Authors, Year, Source, and Cited by. A red box highlights '115 document results'. The first result is 'Cascaded convolutional networks for automatic cephalometric landmark detection' by Zeng, M., Yan, Z., Liu, S., Zhou, Y., and Qiu, L., published in 2021 in Medical Image Analysis, volume 68, page 101904. The interface also shows options to analyze search results, export to RIS, and view citation overviews.

Document title	Authors	Year	Source	Cited by
1 Cascaded convolutional networks for automatic cephalometric landmark detection	Zeng, M., Yan, Z., Liu, S., Zhou, Y., Qiu, L.	2021	Medical Image Analysis 68,101904	0

Figure 4: Scopus AI search results

- ❖ Web of Science (from 1st January 2000 until 9th January 2021): The search resulted in 151 published works.

Figure 5: Web of Science AI search results

Nanotechnology:

- ❖ PubMed (from 1st January 2000 until 9th January 2021): The search resulted in 392 published works.

Figure 6: PubMed NANO search results

- ❖ EBSCO host (from 1st January 2000 until 9th January 2021): The search resulted in 80 published works.

Figure 7: EBSCO host NANO search results

- ❖ ScienceDirect (from 1st January 2000 until 9th January 2021): The search resulted in 25 published works.

Figure 8: ScienceDirect NANO search results

- ❖ Scopus (from 1st January 2000 until 9th January 2021): The search resulted in 94 published works.

94 document results

((TITLE((orthodontic*)) AND TITLE(((nanotechnolog*) OR (nanomedicine) OR (nano*)))))) AND PUBYEAR > 1999 AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "re*)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English") OR LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "French"))

Documents Secondary documents Patents

Analyze search results Show all abstracts Sort on: Date (newest)

Document title	Authors	Year	Source	Cited by
1 Silver nanoparticles in orthodontics, a new alternative in bacterial inhibition: in vitro study <i>Open Access</i>	Jasso-Ruiz, I., Velazquez-Enriquez, U., Scougall-Vilchis, R.J., (...), Sawada, T., Yamaguchi, R.	2020	Progress in Orthodontics 21(1),24	0

Figure 9: Scopus NANO search results

- ❖ Web of Science (from 1st January 2000 until 9th January 2021): The search resulted in 112 published works.

Web of Science InCites Journal Citation Reports Essential Science Indicators EndNote Publons Kopernio Master Journal List JIhed Help English

Web of Science Clarivate Analytics

Search Results: 112 (from All Databases)

You searched for: (TI=(orthodontic*)) AND (TI=((nanotechnolog*) OR (nanomedicine) OR (nano*)))
 Refined by: DOCUMENT TYPES: (ARTICLE OR REVIEW OR CLINICAL TRIAL) AND LANGUAGES: (ENGLISH)
 Timespan: 2000-2021.
 Databases: WOS, KJD, MEDLINE, RSCI, SCIELO.
 Search language=Auto
 ...Less

Sort by: Date Times Cited Usage Count Relevance More

1. Applied Research Glass Ionomer Cement with TiO ₂ Nanoparticles in Orthodontic Treatment. By: Ren, Jiajie; Du, Zhen; Lin, Jiang Journal of nanoscience and nanotechnology Volume: 21 Issue: 2 Pages: 1032-1041 Published: 2021 -Feb-01	Times Cited: 0 (from All Databases) Usage Count
2. Study on the Performance of Titanium Materials Based on Nano Silver Particles in Orthodontic Healing. By: Yan, Weijun; Shao, Ping Journal of nanoscience and nanotechnology Volume: 21 Issue: 2 Pages: 1135-1141 Published: 2021 -Feb-01	Times Cited: 0 (from All Databases) Usage Count

Figure 10: Web of Science NANO search results

Regenerative therapy (Stem cells / Platelet-rich fibrin):

- ❖ PubMed (from 1st January 2000 until 9th January 2021): The search resulted in 194 published works.

NIH National Library of Medicine National Center for Biotechnology Information

PubMed.gov

Search: ("Orthodontics"[Mesh] OR orthodontic*[tiab]) AND ("Stem Cells"[Mesh] OR (s

Advanced Create alert Create RSS User Guide

Save Email Send to Sorted by: Best match Display options

MY NCBI FILTERS 194 results

RESULTS BY YEAR

2000 2021

TEXT AVAILABILITY

Abstract

1 The body's integrated repair kit: Studying mesenchymal **stem cells** for better ligament repair.
 Häfner SJ.
 Cite Biomed J. 2019 Dec42(6):365-370. doi: 10.1016/j.bj.2019.12.001.
 Share PMID: 31948600 Free PMC article.
 In this issue of the Biomedical Journal, we learn that the sport injury-prone knee ligaments might harbour their own repair kit in the form of mesenchymal **stem cells**, and that TERT transformation helps to keep these **cells** longer in culture for more extensive ...

2 Overexpression of osteoprotegerin promotes preosteoblast differentiation to mature osteoblasts.

Figure 11: PubMed RT search results

- ❖ EBSCO host (from 1st January 2000 until 9th January 2021): The search resulted in 52 published works.

Update My Account Not Jihed? Sign in here

New Search Publications Subjects Cited References Images More

Sign Out Folder Preferences Languages Help Exit

EBSCOhost Searching: Dentistry & Oral Sciences Source Choose Databases Library Logo

Search: ((AB (orthodontic*)) OR (TI (orthodontic*))) AND

Select a Field (optional) Search

AND Select a Field (optional) Clear

AND Select a Field (optional)

Basic Search Advanced Search Search History

Refine Results Search Results: 1 - 10 of 52

Relevance Page Options Share

Current Search

Boolean/Phrase:
 ((AB (orthodontic*)) OR (TI (orthodontic*))) AND TI ((stem cell...

Expanders

Apply equivalent subjects

Limiters

Publication Date: 20000101-20211231

1 Amalgamation of allogenic bone graft, **platelet-rich fibrin gel**, and **PRF** membrane in auto-transplantation of an impacted central incisor.

Academic Journal

By: CHAUDHARY, ZAINAB; KUMAR, YUVIKA RAJ; MOHANTY, SUJATA; KHETRAPAL, AMBICA. Contemporary Clinical Dentistry, Apr-Jun2015, Vol. 6 Issue 2, p250-253. 4p. DOI: 10.4103/0976-237X.156059.
 "Social six" teeth refers to the maxillary incisors and canines that play a vital role in the appearance of an individual and absence of any one of them has a significant psycho-social impact. He...

Subjects: TOOTH transplantation; BONE grafting; INCISORS; **FIBRIN**; DENTAL extraction

PDF Full Text (2.2MB)

Figure 12: EBSCO host RT search results

- ❖ ScienceDirect (from 1st January 2000 until 9th January 2021): The search resulted in 32 published works.

Figure 13: ScienceDirect RT search results

- ❖ Scopus (from 1st January 2000 until 9th January 2021): The search resulted in 20 published works.

Figure 14: Scopus RT search results

- ❖ Web of Science (from 1st January 2000 until 9th January 2021): The search resulted in 20 published works.

The screenshot displays the Web of Science search results interface. At the top, navigation links include 'Web of Science', 'InCites', 'Journal Citation Reports', 'Essential Science Indicators', 'EndNote', 'Publons', 'Kopernio', and 'Master Journal List'. The 'Web of Science' logo and 'Clarivate Analytics' branding are visible in the upper right. A search bar at the top right contains 'Search', 'Tools', 'Searches and alerts', 'Search History', and 'Marked List'. Below the search bar, the results are sorted by 'Date' (descending), with options for 'Times Cited', 'Usage Count', 'Relevance', and 'More'. A 'Results: 20 (from All Databases)' box is highlighted in red. The search criteria are: 'You searched for: (TI=(orthodontic*)) AND (TI=(stem cell) OR (Platelet-Rich Fibrin) OR (PRF))'. Refined by: DOCUMENT TYPES: (ARTICLE OR REVIEW). Timespan: 2000-2021. Databases: WOS, KJD, MEDLINE, RSCI, SCIELO. Search language=Auto. A 'Create an alert' button is present. The results list shows two entries: 1. 'Effect of Carbonate Apatite Hydrogel-Advanced Platelet-Rich Fibrin Injection on Osteoblastogenesis during Orthodontic Relapse in Rabbits.' by Alhasyimi, Ananto Ali; Suparwitri, Sri; Christnawati, Christnawati. Published: 2020 -Dec-26 (Epub 2020 Dec 26). 2. 'CREB activation affects mesenchymal stem cell migration and differentiation in periodontal tissues due to orthodontic force.' Both entries show 'Times Cited: 0 (from All Databases)' and 'Usage Count' options. Action buttons include 'Select Page', 'Export...', 'Add to Marked List', 'Analyze Results', and 'Create Citation Report'.

Figure 15: Web of Science RT search results

Appendix 2: Customised data collection form

Sub-topic:

Date of data extraction:

AI:

NANO:

STEM CELLS/PRF:

1. Basic information of the study:

Study ID:	
Title:	
First author:	
Identification site / journal:	
Date of publication:	
Language:	
Country of study:	
Funding / conflicts of interest:	

2. Study Eligibility:

Study Characteristics	Review inclusion criteria			Page/ Para/ Figure #
Type of study (remove designs based on criteria specified in protocol)	<input type="checkbox"/> Randomised Controlled Trial (RCT)	<input type="checkbox"/> Controlled clinical trial (CCT)		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Systematic review/Meta-analysis	<input type="checkbox"/> Case-control		
	<input type="checkbox"/> prospective/retrospective cohort	<input type="checkbox"/> Diagnostic test accuracy		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other design (specify):			
	<i>Does the study design meet the criteria for inclusion?</i>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/> → Exclude	Unclear <input type="checkbox"/>
	Description in text:			

Type of participants (population)	Describe the population included:			
	<input type="checkbox"/> Orthodontic patients	<input type="checkbox"/> Radiographs		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Patients' clinical images	<input type="checkbox"/> Other :		
Types of intervention	Are participants defined as a group having specific social or cultural characteristics?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>	Unclear <input type="checkbox"/>
	Details:			
Comparison	<input type="checkbox"/> Treatment Planning/decision making	<input type="checkbox"/> Treatment delivery		
	Focus of the intervention:			
	Clinical significance and effects on treatment outcome:	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>	Unclear <input type="checkbox"/>
Types of outcome measures	<i>Does the population meet the criteria for inclusion?</i>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/> → Exclude	Unclear <input type="checkbox"/>
	Comparison			
Types of outcome measures	<input type="checkbox"/> Reference standards	<input type="checkbox"/> Therapeutic consensus		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Conventional treatment	<input type="checkbox"/> Other :		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable (details:.....)			
Types of outcome measures	<i>Is the comparator adequate for inclusion?</i>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/> → Exclude	Unclear <input type="checkbox"/>
	List outcomes: [measurable/predictive quantifiable outcome (Yes/ No/ Unclear)?]			
	Outcome measured at a population level or individual level?	Details:		
Types of outcome measures	<i>Do the outcome measures meet the criteria for inclusion?</i>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/> → Exclude	Unclear <input type="checkbox"/>

Summary of Assessment for Inclusion

Include in review <input type="checkbox"/>	Exclude from review <input type="checkbox"/>
Request further details? Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Contact details of authors:
Reasons for exclusion:	
Notes:	

DO NOT PROCEED IF PAPER EXCLUDED FROM REVIEW

3. Characteristics of included studies:

✓ Methods	Descriptions as stated in the report/paper	Page/ Para/ Figure #
• Aim of study	<i>What was the study designed to assess? Are these clearly stated?</i>	
• Design (e.g. parallel, crossover, non-RCT)		
• Method(s) of recruitment of participants		
• Unit of allocation (by individuals, cluster/groups or body parts)		
• Inclusion/exclusion criteria for participation in study		
• Total number of intervention groups		
• Start date		
• End date		
• Duration of participation (from recruitment to last follow-up)		
• Sample size calculation: • What assumptions were made? • Were these assumptions appropriate?	<i>(Yes/ No/ Unclear)</i>	
• Statistical methods used and appropriateness of these methods		

✓ Population	Include information for each group (intervention and controls) under study			Page/ Para/ Figure #
• Total number randomised / Total population				
• Number allocated to each intervention group (no. of individuals)				
• Where there any significant baseline imbalances?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>	Unclear <input type="checkbox"/>	
	Details:			
• Number and reason for withdrawals and exclusions for each intervention group				
• Age (median/range)				
• Sex (male/female)				
• Ethnicity				
• Content (list the strategies intended and delivered)				
• Delivery, timing, frequency, duration, intensity...				
• Providers				
• Duration of intervention				
• Duration of follow-up				
Notes:				

✓ Results	Descriptions as stated in the report/paper		Page/ Para/ Figure #
• Comparison			
• Outcome			
• Type of outcome			
• Results	Intervention results:		
	Control results:		
• Number of participants	Intervention:		
	Control:		
• Missing participants			
• Statistical methods used			

✓ Outcomes	Outcomes	Page/ Para/ Figure #
• Type of outcome (definition)		
• Time points measured		
• Time points reported		
• Is there adequate latency for the outcome to be observed?		
• Unit of measurement		
• How is the outcome reported? Self or study assessor		
• Is it a reliable outcome measure?		
Notes:		

AI EXCLUSIVE SECTION		Page/ Para/ Figure #
• The matter of investigation (study factor)		
• Type of diagnostic imaging or material (modality)		
• Type of AI approach (algorithm architecture)		
• Inclusion/exclusion criteria		
• Participant demographics (age/sex/symptoms)		
• Study methodology (consecutive, random, retrospective, prospective)		
• Start date / end date / duration		
• DTA design		
• Sample size (male/female)		
• Index test description (including criteria for positive test)		
	Criteria for positive test:	
• Reference test description (including criteria for positive test)		
	Criteria for positive test:	
• Persons executing and interpreting index tests (numbers/expertise)		
• Persons executing and interpreting reference test		
• Prevalence		
• Accuracy		
• Sensitivity		
• Specificity		
• ROC		
• AUC		

AI EXCLUSIVE SECTION			
Index test results Threshold=	Condition positive	Condition negative	Total
Index test positive (T+)			
Index test negative (T-)			
Total			
Notes:			

Summary of Assessment for Inclusion/Final decision

Include in review <input type="checkbox"/>		Exclude from review <input type="checkbox"/>	
Request further details?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Contact details of authors:	
Notes:			

Key conclusions of study authors:
Strength and weaknesses/limitations of study:
Reviewer conclusions:

Appendix 3: Risk of bias assessment JBI checklists

JBI CRITICAL APPRAISAL CHECKLIST FOR SYSTEMATIC REVIEWS AND RESEARCH SYNTHESSES

Reviewer _____ Date _____

Author _____ Year _____ Record Number _____

	Yes	No	Unclear	Not applicable
1. Is the review question clearly and explicitly stated?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Were the inclusion criteria appropriate for the review question?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Was the search strategy appropriate?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Were the sources and resources used to search for studies adequate?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Were the criteria for appraising studies appropriate?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Was critical appraisal conducted by two or more reviewers independently?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7. Were there methods to minimize errors in data extraction?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8. Were the methods used to combine studies appropriate?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
9. Was the likelihood of publication bias assessed?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
10. Were recommendations for policy and/or practice supported by the reported data?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
11. Were the specific directives for new research appropriate?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Overall appraisal: Include Exclude Seek further info

Comments (Including reason for exclusion)

*Joanna Briggs Institute. (2017), "Critical Appraisal Tools," [Online]. Available: <https://jbi.global/critical-appraisal-tools>

JBI CRITICAL APPRAISAL CHECKLIST FOR RANDOMIZED CONTROLLED TRIALS

Reviewer _____ Date _____

Author _____ Year _____ Record Number _____

	Yes	No	Unclear	NA
1. Was true randomization used for assignment of participants to treatment groups?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Was allocation to treatment groups concealed?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Were treatment groups similar at the baseline?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Were participants blind to treatment assignment?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Were those delivering treatment blind to treatment assignment?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Were outcomes assessors blind to treatment assignment?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7. Were treatment groups treated identically other than the intervention of interest?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8. Was follow up complete and if not, were differences between groups in terms of their follow up adequately described and analyzed?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
9. Were participants analyzed in the groups to which they were randomized?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
10. Were outcomes measured in the same way for treatment groups?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
11. Were outcomes measured in a reliable way?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
12. Was appropriate statistical analysis used?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
13. Was the trial design appropriate, and any deviations from the standard RCT design (individual randomization, parallel groups) accounted for in the conduct and analysis of the trial?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Overall appraisal: Include Exclude Seek further info

Comments (Including reason for exclusion)

*Joanna Briggs Institute. (2017), "Critical Appraisal Tools," [Online]. Available: <https://jbi.global/critical-appraisal-tools>

JBI CRITICAL APPRAISAL CHECKLIST FOR CASE CONTROL STUDIES

Reviewer _____ Date _____

Author _____ Year _____ Record Number _____

	Yes	No	Unclear	Not applicable
1. Were the groups comparable other than the presence of disease in cases or the absence of disease in controls?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Were cases and controls matched appropriately?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Were the same criteria used for identification of cases and controls?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Was exposure measured in a standard, valid and reliable way?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Was exposure measured in the same way for cases and controls?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Were confounding factors identified?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7. Were strategies to deal with confounding factors stated?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8. Were outcomes assessed in a standard, valid and reliable way for cases and controls?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
9. Was the exposure period of interest long enough to be meaningful?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
10. Was appropriate statistical analysis used?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Overall appraisal: Include Exclude Seek further info

Comments (Including reason for exclusion)

*Joanna Briggs Institute. (2017), "Critical Appraisal Tools," [Online]. Available: <https://jbi.global/critical-appraisal-tools>

JBI CRITICAL APPRAISAL CHECKLIST FOR COHORT STUDIES

Reviewer _____ Date _____

Author _____ Year _____ Record Number _____

	Yes	No	Unclear	Not applicable
1. Were the two groups similar and recruited from the same population?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Were the exposures measured similarly to assign people to both exposed and unexposed groups?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Was the exposure measured in a valid and reliable way?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Were confounding factors identified?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Were strategies to deal with confounding factors stated?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Were the groups/participants free of the outcome at the start of the study (or at the moment of exposure)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7. Were the outcomes measured in a valid and reliable way?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8. Was the follow up time reported and sufficient to be long enough for outcomes to occur?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
9. Was follow up complete, and if not, were the reasons to loss to follow up described and explored?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
10. Were strategies to address incomplete follow up utilized?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
11. Was appropriate statistical analysis used?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Overall appraisal: Include Exclude Seek further info

Comments (Including reason for exclusion)

*Joanna Briggs Institute. (2017), "Critical Appraisal Tools," [Online]. Available: <https://jbi.global/critical-appraisal-tools>

JBI CRITICAL APPRAISAL CHECKLIST FOR DIAGNOSTIC TEST ACCURACY STUDIES

Reviewer _____ Date _____

Author _____ Year _____ Record Number _____

	Yes	No	Unclear	Not applicable
1. Was a consecutive or random sample of patients enrolled?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Was a case control design avoided?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Did the study avoid inappropriate exclusions?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Were the index test results interpreted without knowledge of the results of the reference standard?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. If a threshold was used, was it pre-specified?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Is the reference standard likely to correctly classify the target condition?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7. Were the reference standard results interpreted without knowledge of the results of the index test?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8. Was there an appropriate interval between index test and reference standard?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
9. Did all patients receive the same reference standard?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
10. Were all patients included in the analysis?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Overall appraisal: Include Exclude Seek further info

Comments (Including reason for exclusion)

*Joanna Briggs Institute. (2017), "Critical Appraisal Tools," [Online]. Available: <https://jbi.global/critical-appraisal-tools>

JBI CRITICAL APPRAISAL CHECKLIST FOR QUASI-EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES

Reviewer _____ Date _____

Author _____ Year _____ Record Number _____

	Yes	No	Unclear	Not applicable
1. Is it clear in the study what is the 'cause' and what is the 'effect' (i.e. there is no confusion about which variable comes first)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Were the participants included in any comparisons similar?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Were the participants included in any comparisons receiving similar treatment/care, other than the exposure or intervention of interest?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Was there a control group?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Were there multiple measurements of the outcome both pre and post the intervention/exposure?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Was follow up complete and if not, were differences between groups in terms of their follow up adequately described and analyzed?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7. Were the outcomes of participants included in any comparisons measured in the same way?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8. Were outcomes measured in a reliable way?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
9. Was appropriate statistical analysis used?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Overall appraisal: Include Exclude Seek further info

Comments (Including reason for exclusion)

*Joanna Briggs Institue. (2017), "Critical Appraisal Tools," [Online]. Available: <https://jbi.global/critical-appraisal-tools>

Appendix 4: Oxford Centre for Evidence-Based Medicine 2011 Levels of Evidence.

Question	Step 1 (Level 1*)	Step 2 (Level 2*)	Step 3 (Level 3*)	Step 4 (Level 4*)	Step 5 (Level 5)
How common is the problem?	Local and current random sample surveys (or censuses)	Systematic review of surveys that allow matching to local circumstances**	Local non-random sample**	Case-series**	n/a
Is this diagnostic or monitoring test accurate? (Diagnosis)	Systematic review of cross sectional studies with consistently applied reference standard and blinding	Individual cross sectional studies with consistently applied reference standard and blinding	Non-consecutive studies, or studies without consistently applied reference standards**	Case-control studies, or "poor or non-independent reference standard**	Mechanism-based reasoning
What will happen if we do not add a therapy? (Prognosis)	Systematic review of inception cohort studies	Inception cohort studies	Cohort study or control arm of randomized trial*	Case-series or case-control studies, or poor quality prognostic cohort study**	n/a
Does this intervention help? (Treatment Benefits)	Systematic review of randomized trials or <i>n</i> -of-1 trials	Randomized trial or observational study with dramatic effect	Non-randomized controlled cohort/follow-up study**	Case-series, case-control studies, or historically controlled studies**	Mechanism-based reasoning
What are the COMMON harms? (Treatment Harms)	Systematic review of randomized trials, systematic review of nested case-control studies, <i>n</i> -of-1 trial with the patient you are raising the question about, or observational study with dramatic effect	Individual randomized trial or (exceptionally) observational study with dramatic effect	Non-randomized controlled cohort/follow-up study (post-marketing surveillance) provided there are sufficient numbers to rule out a common harm. (For long-term harms the duration of follow-up must be sufficient.)**	Case-series, case-control, or historically controlled studies**	Mechanism-based reasoning
What are the RARE harms? (Treatment Harms)	Systematic review of randomized trials or <i>n</i> -of-1 trial	Randomized trial or (exceptionally) observational study with dramatic effect			
Is this (early detection) test worthwhile? (Screening)	Systematic review of randomized trials	Randomized trial	Non-randomized controlled cohort/follow-up study**	Case-series, case-control, or historically controlled studies**	Mechanism-based reasoning

* Level may be graded down on the basis of study quality, imprecision, indirectness (study PICO does not match questions PICO), because of inconsistency between studies, or because the absolute effect size is very small; Level may be graded up if there is a large or very large effect size.

** As always, a systematic review is generally better than an individual study.

OCEBM Levels of Evidence Working Group*. "The Oxford 2011 Levels of Evidence". Oxford Centre for Evidence-Based Medicine.

<http://www.cebm.net/index.aspx?o=5653>

* OCEBM Table of Evidence Working Group = Jeremy Howick, Iain Chalmers (James Lind Library), Paul Glasziou, Trish Greenhalgh, Carl Heneghan, Alessandro Liberati, Ivan Moschetti, Bob Phillips, Hazel Thornton, Olive Goddard and Mary Hodgkinson

Appendix 5: GRADE recommendations.

Grade of recommendation	Clarity of risk/benefit	Quality of supporting evidence	Implications
1A Strong recommendation, high-quality evidence	Benefits clearly outweigh risks and burdens, or vice versa	Consistent evidence from well-performed randomized, controlled trials or overwhelming evidence of some other form; further research is unlikely to change our confidence in estimate of benefit and risks	Strong recommendations, can apply to most patients in most circumstances without reservation; clinicians should follow strong recommendation unless clear and compelling rationale for alternative approach is present
1B Strong recommendation, moderate-quality evidence	Benefits clearly outweigh risks and burdens, or vice versa	Evidence from randomized, controlled trials with important limitations (inconsistent results, methodological flaws, indirect or imprecise), or very strong evidence of some other research design; further research (if performed) is likely to have impact on our confidence in estimate of benefit and risks and may change estimate	Strong recommendation and applies to most patients; clinicians should follow strong recommendation unless clear and compelling rationale for alternative approach is present
1C Strong recommendation, low-quality evidence	Benefits appear to outweigh risks and burdens, or vice versa	Evidence from observational studies, unsystematic clinical experience, or randomized, controlled trials with serious flaws; any estimate of effect is uncertain	Strong recommendation, and applies to most patients; some of evidence base supporting recommendation is, however, of low quality
2A Weak recommendation, high-quality evidence	Benefits closely balanced with risks and burdens	Consistent evidence from well-performed randomized, controlled trials or overwhelming evidence of some other form; further research is unlikely to change our confidence in estimate of benefit and risks	Weak recommendation, best action may differ depending on circumstances or patients or societal values
2B Weak recommendation, moderate-quality evidence	Benefits closely balanced with risks and burdens; some uncertainty in estimates of benefits, risks, and burdens	Evidence from randomized, controlled trials with important limitations (inconsistent results, methodological flaws, indirect or imprecise), or very strong evidence of some other research design; further research (if performed) is likely to have impact on our confidence in estimate of benefit and risks and may change estimate	Weak recommendation, alternative approaches likely to be better for some patients under some circumstances
2C Weak recommendation, low-quality evidence	Uncertainty in estimates of benefits, risks, and burdens; benefits may be closely balanced with risks and burdens	Evidence from observational studies, unsystematic clinical experience, or randomized, controlled trials with serious flaws; any estimate of effect is uncertain	Very weak recommendation; other alternatives may be equally reasonable

GRADE, Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation.

Adapted from UpToDate.

<https://www.uptodate.com/home/grading-guide>

Appendix 6: DTA studies designs and outcome measures [22][113].

Systematic reviews of clinical tests

2.2.1.4 Outcome measures

The primary outcome of interest for any systematic review of test accuracy is the data required to populate 2 x 2 contingency tables. These describe the relationship between the results of the index test and the reference standard at a given diagnostic threshold (point at which results are classified as positive or negative). The table includes the number of true positives (TP: those that have the disease and test positive), false positives (FP: those that do not have the disease and test positive), false negatives (FN: those that do have the disease and test negative) and true negatives (TN: those that do not have the disease and test negative). See *Figure 2.1*.

		Reference standard	
		Positive	Negative
Index test	Positive	TP	FP
	Negative	FN	TN

Figure 2.1: The 2x2 contingency table

From the 2 x 2 contingency table, the following commonly used measures of test performance can be calculated:

Sensitivity =

$$\frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

The proportion of people with the target condition who have a positive test result.

Specificity =

$$\frac{TN}{TN + FP}$$

The proportion of people without the target condition who have a negative test result.

Overall accuracy =

$$\frac{TP + TN}{TP + FN + FP + TN}$$

The proportion of people correctly classified by the test.

Positive predictive value =

$$\frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

The probability of disease among persons with a positive test result.

Systematic Reviews

Negative predictive value =

$$\frac{TN}{TN + FN}$$

The probability of non-disease among persons with a negative test result.

Positive likelihood ratio =

$$\frac{\left(\frac{TP}{TP + FN}\right)}{\left(\frac{FP}{FP + TN}\right)} \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{\text{Sensitivity}}{1 - \text{Specificity}}$$

Negative likelihood ratio =

$$\frac{\left(\frac{FN}{TP + FN}\right)}{\left(\frac{TN}{TN + FN}\right)} \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{1 - \text{Sensitivity}}{\text{Specificity}}$$

Likelihood ratios (LR) describe how many times more likely it is that a person with the target condition will receive a particular test result than a person without. Positive likelihood ratios greater than 10 or negative likelihood ratios less than 0.1 are sometimes judged to provide convincing diagnostic evidence.²¹

Diagnostic odds ratio =

$$\frac{TP \times TN}{FP \times FN}$$

Used as an overall indicator of diagnostic performance and calculated as the odds of a positive test result among those with the target condition, divided by the odds of a positive test result among those without the condition.

condition positive (P)

the number of real positive cases in the data

condition negative (N)

the number of real negative cases in the data

true positive (TP)

A test result that correctly indicates the presence of a condition or characteristic

true negative (TN)

A test result that correctly indicates the absence of a condition or characteristic

false positive (FP)

A test result which wrongly indicates that a particular condition or attribute is present

false negative (FN)

A test result which wrongly indicates that a particular condition or attribute is absent

Prevalence

$$\frac{P}{P + N}$$

accuracy (ACC)

$$ACC = \frac{TP + TN}{P + N} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$$

balanced accuracy (BA)

$$BA = \frac{TPR + TNR}{2}$$

F1 score

is the harmonic mean of precision and sensitivity:

$$F_1 = 2 \times \frac{PPV \times TPR}{PPV + TPR} = \frac{2TP}{2TP + FP + FN}$$

Diagnostic odds ratio (DOR)

$$DOR = \frac{LR+}{LR-}$$

Design type	Design name	Description
Single-gate	Cross-sectional study	Recruitment of a consecutive series of participants in whom the diagnosis of interest is suspected. The index test and the reference test is done on all participants and the results of the 2 tests are compared with each other.
	Case-control study	Recruitment of participants with a positive reference test result and participants with a negative reference test result who are randomly selected from the same cohort of participants with the suspicion of the diagnosis of interest. The index is subsequently applied to all participants.
Two-gate	case-control study	Recruitment of participants with a positive reference test result and participants who are diagnosed with alternative conditions that resemble the clinical presentation of the condition of interest. The index test is subsequently applied to all participants.

Adapted from:

[22] Centre for Reviews and Dissemination, Systematic Reviews, University of York, 2008. Published by CRD, University of York. January 2009. ISBN 978-1-900640-47-3 (page 115-116)

[113] Wikipedia contributors. (2022, January 21). Receiver operating characteristic. In Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia. Retrieved 09:18, January 24, 2022, from

[https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Receiver operating characteristic &oldid=1067113055](https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Receiver_operating_characteristic&oldid=1067113055)

Appendix 7: PRISMA 2020 Main Checklist

Topic	No.	Item	Location where item is reported
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review.	Introduction, Page 9
ABSTRACT			
Abstract	2	See the PRISMA 2020 for Abstracts checklist	
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of existing knowledge.	Introduction, Page 9
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	Introduction, Page 9
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	5	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review and how studies were grouped for the syntheses.	Page 12
Information sources	6	Specify all databases, registers, websites, organisations, reference lists and other sources searched or consulted to identify studies. Specify the date when each source was last searched or consulted.	Page 13-14
Search strategy	7	Present the full search strategies for all databases, registers and websites, including any filters and limits used.	Appendix 1
Selection process	8	Specify the methods used to decide whether a study met the inclusion criteria of the review, including how many reviewers screened each record and each report retrieved, whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Page 15-16
Data collection process	9	Specify the methods used to collect data from reports, including how many reviewers collected data from each report, whether they worked independently, any processes for obtaining or confirming data from study investigators, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Page 16
Data items	10a	List and define all outcomes for which data were sought. Specify whether all results that were compatible with each outcome domain in each study were sought (e.g. for all measures, time points, analyses), and if not, the methods used to decide which results to collect.	Appendix 2
	10b	List and define all other variables for which data were sought (e.g. participant and intervention characteristics, funding sources). Describe any assumptions made about any missing or unclear information.	Appendix 2
Study risk of bias assessment	11	Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies, including details of the tool(s) used, how many reviewers assessed each study and whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Page 17
Effect measures	12	Specify for each outcome the effect measure(s) (e.g. risk ratio, mean difference) used in the synthesis or presentation of results.	NA
Synthesis methods	13a	Describe the processes used to decide which studies were eligible for each synthesis (e.g. tabulating the study intervention characteristics and comparing against the planned groups for each synthesis (item 5)).	Page 17
	13b	Describe any methods required to prepare the data for presentation or synthesis, such as handling of missing summary statistics, or data conversions.	Page 17
	13c	Describe any methods used to tabulate or visually display results of individual studies and syntheses.	Page 17
	13d	Describe any methods used to synthesize results and provide a rationale for the choice(s). If meta-analysis was performed, describe the model(s), method(s) to identify the presence and extent of statistical heterogeneity, and software package(s) used.	Page 17 / 51
	13e	Describe any methods used to explore possible causes of heterogeneity among study results (e.g. subgroup analysis, meta-regression).	Page 56
	13f	Describe any sensitivity analyses conducted to assess robustness of the synthesized results.	Page 56-57-58
Reporting bias assessment	14	Describe any methods used to assess risk of bias due to missing results in a synthesis (arising from reporting biases).	Page 17
Certainty assessment	15	Describe any methods used to assess certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for an outcome.	Page 18-19 / Appendix 4-5
RESULTS			
Study selection	16a	Describe the results of the search and selection process, from the number of records identified in the search to the number of studies included in the review, ideally using a flow diagram.	Page 20
	16b	Cite studies that might appear to meet the inclusion criteria, but which were excluded, and explain why they were excluded.	Page 35-36

Topic	No.	Item	Location where item is reported
Study characteristics	17	Cite each included study and present its characteristics.	Page 25-29
Risk of bias in studies	18	Present assessments of risk of bias for each included study.	Page 32-33
Results of individual studies	19	For all outcomes, present, for each study: (a) summary statistics for each group (where appropriate) and (b) an effect estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval), ideally using structured tables or plots.	Page 49-65
Results of syntheses	20a	For each synthesis, briefly summarise the characteristics and risk of bias among contributing studies.	Page 37-46
	20b	Present results of all statistical syntheses conducted. If meta-analysis was done, present for each the summary estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval) and measures of statistical heterogeneity. If comparing groups, describe the direction of the effect.	Page 37-46/53-64
	20c	Present results of all investigations of possible causes of heterogeneity among study results.	Page 53-64
	20d	Present results of all sensitivity analyses conducted to assess the robustness of the synthesized results.	Page 53-64
Reporting biases	21	Present assessments of risk of bias due to missing results (arising from reporting biases) for each synthesis assessed.	Page 32-33
Certainty of evidence	22	Present assessments of certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for each outcome assessed.	Page 34
DISCUSSION			
Discussion	23a	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence.	Page 65-106
	23b	Discuss any limitations of the evidence included in the review.	Page 72
	23c	Discuss any limitations of the review processes used.	Page 72
	23d	Discuss implications of the results for practice, policy, and future research.	Page 87-89
OTHER INFORMATION			
Registration and protocol	24a	Provide registration information for the review, including register name and registration number, or state that the review was not registered.	Page 19
	24b	Indicate where the review protocol can be accessed, or state that a protocol was not prepared.	Page 19
	24c	Describe and explain any amendments to information provided at registration or in the protocol.	Check protocol
Support	25	Describe sources of financial or non-financial support for the review, and the role of the funders or sponsors in the review.	Check protocol
Competing interests	26	Declare any competing interests of review authors.	Check protocol
Availability of data, code and other materials	27	Report which of the following are publicly available and where they can be found: template data collection forms; data extracted from included studies; data used for all analyses; analytic code; any other materials used in the review.	Check protocol

From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *MetaArXiv*. 2020, September 14. DOI: 10.31222/osf.io/v7gm2. For more information, visit: www.prisma-statement.org